

Paving the path towards platform engineering using a comprehensive reference model

Ruben van de Kamp^{1,2}, Kees Bakker², and Zhiming Zhao^{1,3}

¹ Multiscale Networked Systems, University of Amsterdam
1098XH, Amsterdam, The Netherlands
`ruvdkamp@gmail.com`

² Wehkamp, 8021 EV Zwolle, The Netherlands
`{kbakker,ruvdkamp}@wehkamp.nl`

³ LifeWatch Virtual Lab and Innovation Center (VLIC)
1098XH, Amsterdam, The Netherlands
`z.zhao@uva.nl`

Abstract. Amidst the growing popularity of platform engineering, promising improved productivity and enhanced developer experience through an engineering platform, e.g., an Internal Developer Platform (IDP), this paper addresses the prevalent challenge of a lack of a shared understanding in the field and the complications in defining effective, customized strategies. Introducing a definitive Platform Engineering Reference Model (PE-RM) based on the Reference Model for Open Distributed Processing (RM-ODP) framework to provide a common understanding. This model offers a structured framework for software organizations to create tailored platform engineering strategies and realize the full potential of platform engineering. By facilitating a shared vocabulary and providing a roadmap for implementation, this paper aims to mitigate prevailing complexities and accelerate the adoption and effectiveness of platform engineering across organizations, showcasing the added value.

Keywords: Platform engineering · Reference model · System modeling · Cloud infrastructure · Development Lifecycle

1 Introduction

The digital age has initiated substantial transformations across all industries, making digitalization an imperative for survival in today's volatile market landscape [3]. This transition has amplified the importance of software development and deployment, with methodologies like DevOps and Agile acting as instrumental drivers of this digital revolution [7, 18]. Agile, advocating adaptability and customer collaboration, and DevOps, fostering cooperation between development and operations teams, enhancing the efficiency and quality of software delivery [2, 15].

Amid increasing technological complexity, platform engineering is emerging as a promising discipline.⁴ It focuses on altering the engineering culture and

⁴ <https://platformengineering.org/blog/what-is-platform-engineering>

creating an engineering platform, e.g., an Internal Developer Platform (IDP), to offer self-service capabilities for software development teams in the cloud-native era [10, 20]. Yet, interpretation variations tied to personal perspectives and organizational contexts could render the definition ambiguous.

Platform engineering adoption faces challenges such as inconsistencies in understanding across different stakeholders and the interchangeable use of terminology such as “Internal Developer Platform” and “DevOps”, which could create communication hurdles and compromise the efficiency of technological strategies.⁵ Moreover, clear guidelines about the separation of accountability between different types of teams are essential. Further addressing the team types differentiated by team topologies [22]. Hence, standardizing the platform engineering terminology is critical to establishing a shared understanding.

Another significant challenge involves crafting a tailored platform engineering strategy, which requires extensive knowledge of the organization’s processes and culture. It also necessitates comprehending how implementing platform engineering could alter these facets. The complexity in this paradigm shift to platform engineering extends to organizational changes, architectural design, technology selection, and operational management[4].⁶ To address these challenges, the paper focuses on the following research questions:

- How to model platform engineering in the context of a software company?
- How to define a customized platform engineering design tailored to a specific organization?
- How to effectively construct a technical platform engineering implementation?

To answer these RQs, we proposed a reference model for platform engineering grounded and validated in a case study and experiments. This Platform Engineering Reference Model (PE-RM) seeks to clarify the nature and scope of platform engineering, bridging comprehension gaps among various stakeholders. Further validated and applied in a case study that proposes both a conceptual design and technical implementation guided by the PE-RM as a guideline and example to showcase the added value of platform engineering.

The paper is based on work done in the thesis [14] and unfolds as follows. Section 2 discusses related work. Section 3 presents the Platform Engineering Reference Model. Section 4 offers a case study in which a conceptual design and technical implementation with experiments are conducted. Section 5 discusses the achievements and lessons learned. Finally, section 6 presents the conclusion and future work.

2 Related work

Three streams of related work are relevant to this paper: publications detailing system proposals inclusive of platform engineering characteristics, industrial

⁵ <https://www.gartner.com/en/articles/what-is-platform-engineering>

⁶ <https://thenewstack.io/platform-engineering/platform-engineering-challenges-and-solutions>

articles and whitepapers on platform engineering, and publications presenting reference models to depict methodologies and architectures. Extensive research has been conducted on the multifaceted nature of platforms and their diverse applications, yielding various definitions [12]. The first use of the concept of platform was the “product platform”, and it was defined as specific modular product architectures that help develop product families [13, 16]. Platforms can be categorized in different ways, one of which is innovation platforms and transaction platforms [5]. The concept of an innovation platform lies closest to the platform engineering philosophy. Governance within the platform’s technological system is established through technological interfaces and standards, leveraging modularity [1]. This underscores the pivotal role of the platform designer, functioning as an architect to ensure the seamless integration of different platform components—an aspect synonymous with the role of platform engineering. A seminal study delves into platform-based product development in enterprise application development, emphasizing its crucial role in enhancing efficiency and flexibility [24]. The authors highlight the significance of increased academic research in this domain and advocate for closer collaboration between academia and industry. However, in contrast to the Platform Engineering Reference Model (PE-RM), this study does not provide a comprehensive roadmap for implementing platform engineering within an organization.

Next, regarding articles pushed from the industry related to platform engineering, the most prominent is the IDP reference model proposed by Humanitec [11]. Since platform engineering heavily relies on an engineering platform e.g., Internal Developer Platform (IDP), Humanitec proposes a reference architecture for such IDP. The IDP architecture provides insight into its possible realization with specific tools and the significance of its components. However, this reference architecture delves into specific tool choices, which reduces the applicability of this architecture since this can depend on individual preferences and pre-existing toolsets. Together with the organizational aspect and a general integration for platform engineering the PE-RM provides a more comprehensive model.

As this research adopts an ontology-based approach to propose a reference model, we provide related work concerning approaches of this type. Various reference models exist for similar methodologies, such as the DevOps Reference Architecture (DRA) is an architecture proposed to deploy IoT into the cloud [8]. This DRA consists of four different models: DRA contextual model, conceptual model, logical model, and physical model. Lastly, research into a software architecture framework for quality-aware DevOps has been conducted [6]. The authors state that many stakeholders are involved in DevOps but do not have a direct relation to the product but account for the product’s organizational stability. The primary distinction between these reference models and the PE-RM lies in their scope of application. While DevOps and Agile are primarily geared toward enhancing team-level processes and collaboration, platform engineering aims to drive improvements across the entire organization.

In summary, while extensive research has delved into various platforms and their unique characteristics, there exists a noticeable scarcity of literature specif-

ically addressing platform engineering as a distinct methodology. The limited available literature presents diverse viewpoints, underscoring a lack of consensus on the subject. This underlines the limited support in identifying and elucidating what platform engineering necessitates and its potential applications. The current reference architecture for platform engineering appears to be inadequate, and since platform engineering is different from other methodologies, the existing reference models are insufficient for platform engineering. Therefore, this paper offers significant value by providing a comprehensive reference model of platform engineering, integrating both technical and organizational aspects. The Reference Model for Open Distributed Processing (RM-ODP) is used to facilitate the creation of this reference model. The RM-ODP is a conceptual framework for designing and describing distributed systems [17, 21]. Moreover, the RM-ODP has been used to model complex IT systems, e.g., the reference model for environmental research infrastructure [9, 19].

3 Platform Engineering Reference Model

This section introduces the Platform Engineering Reference Model (PE-RM). Based on the existing related work, a general understanding of platform engineering is needed and will be achieved by creating a multi-viewpoint reference model. It is an ensemble of viewpoints that illustrate the principal objects within each viewpoint, their organization by the platform engineering lifecycles, and their correlations with objects defined in other viewpoints. The viewpoints suggested by the PE-RM aim to be as loosely coupled as possible to enable parallel design and development efforts across the organization. The PE-RM outlines five viewpoints (figure 1), and the following subsections explain the methodology and elaborate on these viewpoints.

Fig. 1: The five viewpoints of the Platform Engineering RM.

3.1 Methodology

An iterative approach was used to acquire a comprehensive understanding of platform engineering, which started by conducting a series of interviews with numerous experts, each from diverse professional backgrounds and roles. The organization investigated already manifested aspects of platform engineering, and a need for greater standardization of terminology was apparent to enhance its applicability in this and other organizations. Therefore, we interviewed industry experts outside the organization for a more holistic understanding. Consequently, the RM-ODP framework was leveraged to express the platform engineering terminology, refining its interpretation and application.

Fig. 2: Visualisation for Methodology of the Platform Engineering Reference Model.

The first step in developing this reference model involved interviewing eight software engineering experts with varied roles and backgrounds within and outside the organization (see figure 2). Their perceptions guided the formation of the viewpoints in the second step. Its validity was assessed via additional interviews and comparison with related work in step three. The primary validation of the reference model was done in the case study consisting of a conceptual design, technical implementation, and experiments to help showcase the added value and applicability of the PE-RM. Notably, the methodology adopted an iterative approach, necessitating continuous refinement of the reference model in light of fresh insights and varied perspectives. This recursive cycle of refining greatly enhanced the model's maturity and reliability.

3.2 Enterprise viewpoint

The enterprise viewpoint focuses on the organizational context of the domain in which the designed systems are intended to operate. This viewpoint concentrates

on the lifecycle, stakeholders (roles), and activities that the adoption of platform engineering will introduce. The enterprise viewpoint is intended to cover the process changes and how this impact different lifecycles, teams, and their responsibilities. With these concepts, the following lifecycles are introduced:

- *Platform engineering lifecycle* is the lifecycle in which the engineering platform will be introduced and maintained by a newly created platform team. It includes phases that help the platform team create a platform that fulfills the needs of the development teams and improves the platform.
- *Application lifecycle* is the lifecycle in which the development teams create business value while using the engineering platform to increase productivity and developer experience. With platform engineering, the continuous development lifecycle will not be affected.

With these lifecycles, new roles have to be introduced and assigned. The roles can be divided into two categories: *active* and *passive* roles. See table 1.

Table 1: Part of platform engineering roles and stakeholders.

Active role	Mission	Typical behavior
<i>Platform team</i>	Build and support an engineering platform to increase the productivity of development teams.	Maintain the platform. Support the development teams.
<i>Enterprise architects</i>	Investigate (platform) improvements and improve overall software processes.	Investigate software processes. Kickstart platform engineering adoption.
<i>Development teams</i>	Use the platform to increase productivity when creating business value.	Develop applications. Utilize platform
<i>Development guilds</i>	Groups of developers with the same expertise responsible for best practice adoption.	Maintain golden paths. Explore best practices
Passive role	Mission	Typical behavior
<i>Engineering platform</i>	Improve the application lifecycle by offering self-service capabilities.	Offers self-service capabilities.
<i>Cloud platform</i>	The platform where applications and services are running in production.	Running applications to deliver a working system.

Each role engages differently in the platform engineering and application lifecycles, with the platform team more focused on the former and development teams on the latter. As stakeholders of the engineering platform, development teams can request new features, prompting the platform engineering lifecycle. Typically, if a tool is used and maintained separately by different development teams, it will become part of the platform team’s responsibility.

3.3 Information viewpoint

The information viewpoint specification enables the clear and concise representation of the information objects consumed and produced by the phases in the

platform engineering and application lifecycles introduced in the enterprise viewpoint. Providing a standard model, that can be referenced throughout a complete design specification, assures that the same interpretation of information is applied at all levels, including the activities related to these objects. The PE-RM information viewpoint aims to achieve a shared model for the design activity, given that it can cover a federation of tools and integration of legacy systems.

The main modeling concepts of the information viewpoint are *information objects* and *action objects*, which are explained in table 2 and 3. From the information viewpoint, the emphasis is on the data, their evolution, and the activities which enable that evolution. The action objects are based on the stakeholders and roles introduced from the enterprise viewpoint. Based on the lifecycles defined in the enterprise viewpoint, the information and action objects will also have relationships since action objects cannot modify all information objects.

One of the key information objects that are introduced is the golden path. The term "golden path" refers to a set of best practices, tools, libraries, and architecture choices supported by the organization and maintained by development guilds. By adhering to the golden path, development teams can more effectively build, test, and deploy applications with greater consistency, reliability, and speed ⁷.

Table 2: Part of the platform engineering lifecycle information and action objects.

Information object	Description
<i>Architecture design</i>	Displays the tools used separated into different planes.
<i>Roadmap</i>	A planning of the platform to track the development progress.
<i>Backlog</i>	A list of functionalities, based on the roadmap and architecture, readable for the platform team.
<i>Deliverable</i>	The functionalities created by the platform team, which could be different based on the type of functionality.
<i>Release</i>	A bundle of new platform features deployed at a fixed time.
<i>Platform version</i>	The version of the platform, including an announcement, documentation, and change logs.
<i>Golden paths</i>	Step-by-step tutorials to execute a task utilizing the platform.
<i>Service catalog</i>	Centralized system that keeps track of ownership and metadata for all the software (components).
Action object	Description
<i>Enterprise architect</i>	Helps with the architecture design of the platform and roadmap based on new feature requests and observations.
<i>Product owner platform team</i>	Responsible for the platform roadmap and backlog with incoming feature requests.
<i>Platform team</i>	Responsible for the platform by building deliverables, releases, and deploying new platform versions.
<i>Development Guild</i>	Responsible for the golden paths.

⁷ <https://engineering.atspotify.com/2020/08/how-we-use-golden-paths-to-solve-fragmentation-in-our-software-ecosystem/>

Table 3: Part of the application lifecycle information and action objects.

Information object	Description
<i>Architecture</i>	The design of the application domain to deliver business value.
<i>Application domain</i>	The resources and applications needed to deliver business value, based on the architecture.
<i>Resources</i>	The application domain resources provisioned by the platform.
<i>Application</i>	The code created and maintained by the development team.
<i>Platform feature request</i>	The requests made by the development teams for the need for specific tools and support in the platform.
Action object	Description
<i>Development team</i>	Maintains and provisions the architectural design of the application domain and can request platform features.

3.4 Computational viewpoint

The computational viewpoint specification models the components that provide different functionalities for processing data assets and allows the lifecycle to continue to other phases. The computational viewpoint is concerned with developing the high-level design of the processes and applications supporting the platform’s self-service capabilities and activities done during the lifecycles. The viewpoint expresses models in terms of functional components of the engineering platform and how different parts will interact with typed interfaces by performing a sequence of activities. The computational viewpoint specifications refer to specific parts of the information viewpoint. Table 4 presents different operations.

Table 4: Part of the platform engineering operations.

Operation	Description
<i>Utilize golden paths</i>	Development teams using golden paths to adopt best practices and use the engineering platform.
<i>Maintain golden paths</i>	Development guilds maintaining golden paths based on platform support and best practices.
<i>Provision application domain</i>	Based on the architecture, provisioning the application domain, including all necessary services.
<i>Deploy applications</i>	Development teams deploying their application using the engineering platform.

The main modeling concepts of the Computational Viewpoint are the different platform components, their passive and active interfaces, and the relevant configuration in which objects are integrated to provide their services. Depending on the context and organization, these operations can be different. The computational viewpoint operations can be translated into golden paths, which can be used to execute these sequences, emphasizing the importance of golden paths.

3.5 Engineering viewpoint

The primary goal of the engineering viewpoint is to represent the distribution of components among different software systems and tools. The engineering viewpoint tackles the problem of diversity in platform structure and gives the prescriptions for supporting the necessary abstract computational interactions in various situations, explained in the computational viewpoint. The engineering viewpoint is also concerned with providing the management with guarantees (transparency). These assurances are understood to manifest in planes that enable an engineering platform to substantiate the platform engineering discipline. It will help identify the various improvements that must be made as an organization to fully adopt platform engineering with a simplified overview and separation of concerns. Given that most organizations will already possess an engineering setup, it can be enhanced by reshaping it according to the model offered from the engineering perspective.

The main modeling concepts of the engineering viewpoint are engineering objects, containers, and channels. However, to ensure that the platform engineering is correctly acknowledged, the engineering platform has been separated into different planes based on the IDP reference architecture of Humanitec [11].⁸ The resource plane can be seen as the foundation for the platform and applications. The engineering platform can be separated into two features: construct applications and enable applications to run in production, where the latter is not explicitly modeled in this diagram.

Fig. 3: Planes and components of the engineering platform.

⁸ <https://humanitec.com/reference-architectures>

3.6 Technology viewpoint

Technology viewpoint specifications represent the concrete dependencies between design and implementation. The technology viewpoint is concerned with managing real-world constraints, such as existing application platforms, tools, or restrictions based on requirements and budget. The adoption of platform engineering will rarely have the luxury of being a greenfield project [23]. Therefore this viewpoint brings together information about the existing infrastructure and technology stack. It is concerned with the selection of universal standards to be used in the system and the allocation and configuration of resources. It represents the software components and techniques of the implemented system based on the engineering viewpoint specifications. In table 5, the diagram represents the platform components and the best practices/standards.

Table 5: Part of the best practices of the engineering platform components.

Plane	Component	Description	Best practices
Developer control plane	IDE	The local development environment.	IDE & Backlog management
	Developer Portal	Frontend for developers to interact with the platform.	Developer portal & ChatBot
	Provisioning service	Engine to provision application domains and ensure governance is in place.	Microservice
	Version control / IaC	Location to store code.	Git & IaC
Integration & Delivery plane	CI pipeline	Pipeline to build code and push artifacts to the registry.	Containerization
	Registry	Location to store releasable artifacts like docker containers and packages.	Repositories
	CD pipeline	Pipeline to update the environment with the artifacts, triggered by CI or manually.	Containerization
Monitoring & Logging plane	Observability	Gathering and showing metrics (dashboards, alerts).	Metrics Scraper & Elastic storage
	Logging	Storing, and querying logs created by the application running in production.	Elastic storage & Querying tool
Security plane	Secrets & identity management	Secrets that will be injected as soon as the application is deployed.	Role management & secret manager
Resource plane	Compute	The resources used to run the application based on given configurations.	Docker & Kubernetes
	Data & storage	The resources that can store data and other artifacts like images or files.	Databases & file storage
	Networking	Handles the networking tasks like load balancing and reachability.	Load balancer & gateways
	Services	Services that are needed to make the application domain work.	Example: message broker

This viewpoint also has an essential role in the management of testing conformance to the overall specification, because it specifies the information required from implementers to support this testing. The main modeling concepts of the technology viewpoint are *components*, *standards*, and in our case, *best practices*. Since the engineering platform is a central collection of tools, services, and automated workflows, which can differ for each organization and environment, this viewpoint does not focus on state-of-the-art tools, unlike the Humanitec IDP reference architecture [11].

4 Case study

Several research activities were conducted to implement and validate the proposed Platform Engineering Reference Model in a software organization and context. We initially assess the viability of generating a conceptual design using the reference model within an organizational context to verify its utility in platform engineering design. This is followed by creating a basic proof-of-concept, derived from the conceptual design, for an engineering platform to test its technical relevance. Finally, we undertake experiments to evaluate the implementation's effectiveness and added value. The case study for the conceptual design is carried out in a Dutch online retailer.

4.1 Conceptual design

This case study utilized the PE-RM to design platform engineering for a software-based Dutch online retailer. The analysis illuminated the organization's current practices, highlighting areas for improvement. A significant finding was the communication gap between the platform and development teams, affecting productivity and development processes. This insight emphasized the need for improved organizational cooperation, leading to the suggestion of development guilds, platform versioning, and the introduction of golden paths for standardized application provisioning. These golden paths ensure not only consistent application onboarding but also reduce cognitive load on developers.

The computational viewpoint indicated that golden paths could refine operational processes, simplifying operations and boosting software quality. Based on the performance analysis, there is a significant improvement that can be made with the adoption of golden paths and standardization. From the engineering and technology viewpoint, integrating tools like the Backstage developer portal would bolster platform engineering capabilities, fostering better communication and service discoverability. The PE-RM's application in the study showcased its capability to offer tailored platform engineering solutions. The study reinforced that successful platform engineering is not just about new tools but aligning them with organizational needs. Embracing a developer portal will streamline integration and adoption, laying a foundation for efficient platform engineering, serving as a blueprint for other organizations.

4.2 Technical implementation

Derived from the observations and opportunities gathered in the conceptual design, we did a separate technical implementation as proof of concept. The architectural design for the engineering platform is illustrated in figure 4. Guided by the PE-RM’s engineering and technology viewpoints, this design highlights the platform’s components, their functions, and associated design choices, underscoring the value of an engineering platform.

Fig. 4: Technical implementation: engineering platform infrastructure design.

The prototype’s primary goal is to demonstrate key platform engineering features, rather than tool choices. To achieve this, we used Otomi⁹, an open-source Platform as a Service system. The framework integrates multiple tools tailored to fit our needs. Additionally, we’ve customized it to add new functions, including integration with tools like Backstage.

This technical execution focuses on two crucial areas of the application lifecycle that demonstrate platform engineering’s significance: **(1)** application domain provisioning and **(2)** observability and logging. For domain provisioning, we’ve introduced golden paths that guide development teams in setting up the application domain, as shown in figure 5. These paths handle application provisioning, pipelines, metrics exposure, and deployment configurations. For observability and logging, utilizing these golden paths ensures alignment with the platform’s default logging and metric tools. There are ready-made dashboards, offering precise and default metrics across all applications. If an application logs messages, these are automatically collected, enhancing visibility. Thus, the platform offers self-service features that refine development teams’ application lifecycles.

⁹ <https://otomi.io>

Fig. 5: Technical implementation: golden paths.

4.3 Experiments

Several experiments were conducted to validate and highlight the value of the technical implementation. To measure the engineering platform’s usability and productivity, we conducted a study assessing software developers’ perceived productivity enhancements. We also showcased a demo and distributed a questionnaire to platform experts for their feedback. Ten participants, ranging from students to senior developers, were involved in the productivity and usability study. These participants performed different tasks and afterward completed a questionnaire. Additionally, five platform experts, including engineers, architects, and tech leads, participated in another study to gather a diverse set of feedback.

Two key performance metrics emerged from the productivity analysis in the conceptual design: application onboarding time and developer onboarding time. The application onboarding time is the time it takes to create a new application and get it into production with all the requirements. The developer onboarding time is the time it takes for a developer to deploy their first application into production. Before the study, participants estimated an average of 7 hours to onboard an application. However, the results showed a significant reduction in onboarding time when using an engineering platform (figure 6).

Usability feedback was generally positive. The platform’s ease of use averaged a rating of 4 out of 5, with participants experiencing that 90% of the work was managed by the platform. Moreover, we observed that the most likable features are Backstage and golden paths, as it support developers onboard new applications, including configurations and standardization. From the platform

Fig. 6: Experimentation results.

perspective, feedback underlined the implementation as exemplary but noted potential integration challenges with existing systems due to Otomi. Nevertheless, all experts acknowledged its value and recommended this technical approach.

5 Discussion

During this research, we have achieved several milestones in relation to platform engineering. First, we have modeled platform engineering within a comprehensive reference model by deploying a multi-viewpoint approach. This method allowed us to dissect and explore platform engineering from various angles, resulting in a rich and detailed model that captures the inherent complexities of this discipline. Second, we delved into the complexity of implementing platform engineering by conducting a case study in which we created a conceptual design and technical implementation guided by the PE-RM. This technical implementation is further validated by experiments gaining insight into the added value of platform engineering by evaluating the productivity of developers. Third, we validated our reference model, demonstrating its utility and validity. Our validation confirmed that the model is theoretically sound and practically applicable, making it a valuable tool for organizations. The experiments exposed the added value of a drastically reduced onboarding time. Together, these achievements underscore the potential and value of the reference model as a guideline for organizations seeking to adopt platform engineering.

Regardless, challenges arise due to the lack of scientific research in this area, making systematic reviews difficult. Additional empirical data collection and analysis are critical to further support the model's validity. The experiments are focused on a select number of metrics, which do not cover all the aspects of platform engineering integration. The context-dependent nature of platform engineering may limit the model's broad applicability, as implementations could vary significantly across organizations. The environment in which a platform is introduced could also play an important role, where we focussed on a cloud environment and not on an on-premises environment. While the model is deemed

beneficial for numerous organizations, it may not align seamlessly with all contexts, representing a recognized limitation. To strengthen and increase the relevance of the proposed model, further, diverse validation efforts, both quantitative and qualitative, across different organizational types are recommended. This could help to investigate the trade-off that must be made between the costs that integrating platform engineering entails versus what it delivers, which is currently not covered in this research.

6 Conclusion & Future work

To conclude, in this paper, an understanding of platform engineering is presented through a reference model based on the RM-ODP framework. The validation and implementation of this reference model within a software organization are demonstrated, including a conceptual design and technical implementation. The proposed reference model will be a helpful tool for organizations to adopt platform engineering efficiently. While our findings are based on a single case study, we assume that this reference model applies to different types of organizations.

Future work involves three fronts: explore the integration of platform engineering across different organizational styles, enabling the model's customization for broader contexts and thus enhancing its applicability and utility; implement platform engineering to gather more empirical data on the effects of platform engineering integration in the long term, including a broader range of productivity metrics; and investigate the trade-off between the investment of integrating platform engineering and the benefits it brings to the organization.

Acknowledgements This research is partially funded by the EU Horizon program under grant agreements 101094227 (BlueCloud 2026 project) and 860627 (CLARIFY project) and partially supported by LifeWatch ERIC and Dutch NWO LTER-LIFE project.

References

1. Baldwin, C.Y.: Design rules, volume 2: how technology shapes organizations. Harvard Business School Research Paper Series pp. 19–042 (2018)
2. Beck, K., Beedle, M., Bennekum, V., et al.: The agile manifesto (2001)
3. Bharadwaj, A., Sawy, O.A.E., Pavlou, P.A., Venkatraman, N.: Digital business strategy: Toward a next generation of insights. *MIS Quarterly* **37**(2), 471–482 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.25300/misq/2013/37:2.3>
4. Campbell, M.: Platform engineering challenges: Small teams, build versus buy, and building the wrong thing. *InfoQ* (2023)
5. Cusumano, M.A., Gawer, A., Yoffie, D.B.: The business of platforms: Strategy in the age of digital competition, innovation, and power, vol. 320. Harper Business New York (2019)
6. Di Nitto, E., Jamshidi, P., Guerriero, M., Spais, I., Tamburri, D.A.: A software architecture framework for quality-aware devops. p. 12–17. QUDOS 2016, Association for Computing Machinery (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2945408.2945411>

7. Dingsøy, T., Nerur, S., Balijepally, V., Moe, N.B.: A decade of agile methodologies: Towards explaining agile software development. *Journal of Systems and Software* **85**(6), 1213–1221 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2012.02.033>
8. Ghantous, G.B., Gill, A.Q.: Devops reference architecture for multi-cloud iot applications. In: 2018 IEEE 20th Conference on Business Informatics (CBI). vol. 01, pp. 158–167 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1109/CBI.2018.00026>
9. de la Hidalga, A.N., Hardisty, A., Martin, P., Magagna, B., Zhao, Z.: The EN-VRI Reference Model, pp. 61–81. Springer International Publishing, Cham (2020). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-52829-4_4
10. Humanitec: State of platform engineering report. Tech. rep., Humanitec (2022)
11. Humanitec: Reference architecture for an enterprise-grade internal developer platform built with humanitec on aws. Tech. rep., Humanitec (2023)
12. Jacobides, M.G., Cennamo, C., Gawer, A.: Externalities and complementarities in platforms and ecosystems: From structural solutions to endogenous failures. *Research Policy* **53**(1), 104906 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2023.104906>
13. Jiao, J., Simpson, T.W., Siddique, Z.: Product family design and platform-based product development: a state-of-the-art review. *Journal of intelligent Manufacturing* **18**, 5–29 (2007). <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.1007/s10845-007-0003-2>
14. van de Kamp, R., Bakker, K., Zhao, Z.: Paving the path towards platform engineering using a comprehensive reference model. Ph.D. thesis, University of Amsterdam (Sep 2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8379087>
15. Kim, G., Humble, J., Debois, P., Willis, J., Forsgren, N.: *The DevOps handbook: How to create world-class agility, reliability, & security in technology organizations*. IT Revolution (2021)
16. Krishnan, V., Gupta, S.: Appropriateness and impact of platform-based product development. *Management Science* **47**(1), 52–68 (Jan 2001). <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.47.1.52.10665>
17. Linington, P.F., Milosevic, Z., Tanaka, A., Vallecillo, A.: Building enterprise systems with odp - an introduction to open distributed processing. In: Chapman and Hall / CRC innovations in software engineering and software development (2011)
18. Lwakatare, L.E., Kuvaja, P., Oivo, M.: Dimensions of devops. In: Lassenius, C., Dingsøy, T., Paasivaara, M. (eds.) *Agile Processes in Software Engineering and Extreme Programming*. pp. 212–217. Springer International Publishing (2015). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-18612-2_19
19. Martin, P., Magagna, B., Liao, X., Zhao, Z.: Semantic Linking of Research Infrastructure Metadata, pp. 226–246. Springer International Publishing, Cham (2020). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-52829-4_13
20. Nigel Kersten, K.M., Michael Stahnke, C.O.: State of devops report. Puppet (2021)
21. Raymond, K., Armstrong, L.: Reference Model of Open Distributed Processing (RM-ODP): Introduction, pp. 3–14. Springer US, Boston, MA (1995). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-34882-7_1
22. Skelton, M., Pais, M.: Team topologies: organizing business and technology teams for fast flow. *IT Revolution* (2019)
23. Sousa, C.D.: Brownfield redevelopment versus greenfield development: A private sector perspective on the costs and risks associated with brownfield redevelopment in the greater toronto area. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management* **43**(6), 831–853 (2000). <https://doi.org/10.1080/09640560020001719>
24. Zhou, J., Ji, Y., Zhao, D., Liu, J.: Platform engineering in enterprise application development. In: 2010 International Conference on E-Business and E-Government. pp. 112–115 (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICEE.2010.36>